
Principles of Public-Private Partnerships in the Context of a Road Network

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MSc. Construction Project Management

Contracts and Procurement

D31PZ

OCTOBER 2015

HERIOT WATT UNIVERSITY
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CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE IN SUSTAINABLE BUILDING DESIGN

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1 – Introduction

Nowadays in most developed countries governments face the challenges of developing the growing demand on infrastructures services. There is an international consensus that countries with a well-developed road network are associated with a better economic performance and quality of life. Therefore, governments are always trying to find ways to develop their road network and transportation systems in order to meet their economic, political and social needs. Consequently, the need to build new roads or refurbishing, widening and extending existing roads is increasing (WORLDBANK¹, 2015).

Investments in road infrastructures are expensive and governments face the problem of having the need to implement multiple projects at the same time with budget constraints and limited traditional funding sources. The development of new routes of procurement had to be found and governments brought the investment of the private sector as a partnership has an attractive alternative to traditional funding sources to increase and improve the supply of infrastructures services (QUIUM, 2011).

The aim of this report is to explain to the Ministry of Transportation the principles of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), its merits and demerits in the context of road infrastructures network and the different formats that could be used. An appropriated format of PPPs will be studied and proposed for the development of a new road project and for the maintenance of existing ones. Traditional routes of procurement will be taken into consideration and compared with the PPP formats.

2 – The Principles of Public-Private Partnerships in Road Infrastructure Project

Public-private partnerships (Table 1) are becoming an important tool for governments to procure and delivery infrastructures and services making use of the resources and expertise of the private sector. When governments face problems with underdeveloped infrastructures and are required to improve efficient services, partnerships that include the private sector, can give access to their experiences, innovation and more importantly bring finance (OECD, 2011) (WORLDBANK², 2015).

Table 1- Different definitions of PPP (adapted from OECD,2011).

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Korea defines a public-private partnership project as a project to build and operate infrastructure such as road, port, railway, school and environmental facilities – which have traditionally been constructed and run by government funding – with private capital, thus tapping the creativity and efficiency of private sector. • South Africa defines a public-private partnership as a commercial transaction between a government institution and a private partner in which the private party either performs an institutional function on behalf of the institution for a specified or indefinite period, or acquires the use of state property for its own commercial purposes for a specified or indefinite period. The private party receives a benefit for performing the function or by utilizing state property, either by way of compensation from a revenue fund, charges or fees collected by the private party from users or customers of a service provided to them, or a combination of such compensation and such charges or fees. • The United Kingdom defines a public-private partnership as "...arrangements typified by joint working between the public and private sectors. In their broadest sense they can cover all types of collaboration across the private-public sector interface involving collaborative working together and risk sharing to deliver policies, services and infrastructure." (HMT, Infrastructure Procurement: Delivering Long-Term Value, March 2008). The most common type of PPP in the UK is the Private Finance Initiative. A Private Finance Initiative is an arrangement whereby the public sector contracts to purchase services, usually derived from an investment in assets, from the private sector on a long-term basis, often between 15 to 30 years. This includes concessions and franchises, where a private sector partner takes on the responsibility for providing a public service, including maintaining, enhancing or constructing the necessary infrastructure. • The State of Victoria (Australia) defines a public-private partnership as relating to the provision of infrastructure and any related ancillary service which involve private investment or financing, with a present value of payments for a service to be made by the government (and/or by consumers) of more than AUD 10 mil. during the period of a partnership that do not relate to the general procurement of services.

PPPs combine the skills and resources of both the public and private sector, the private partner may be responsible for the design, construction, financing, operation and management of a capital asset or the delivery of a service to the public sector (WORLDBANK², 2015). In the PPP, the government specifies the quality and quantity of the service it requires from the private partner. The PPPs are usually of higher capital value than traditional routes of procurement mainly because the cost of borrowing money is higher for the private sector than for the public sector. However, PPPs are particularly attractive to governments as they provide access to new infrastructures without the capital cost of construction, consequently, the private partner will receive either a stream of payments from the government, user charges

levied directly on the end users, or a combination of both (OECD,2011; OYEGOKE,2015).

Regarding the use of PPPs in the development of road and transportation infrastructures, in most EU countries these schemes have been used as an important way to develop new infrastructures, refurbishing and maintain existing roads without the need for the state to borrow large amounts of capital required to build such infrastructures leaving this responsibility to the private sector (Macário *et al.*, 2015). Governments are using these mechanisms to provide better services and infrastructures to the population as well as to lever the economy providing more investment without increasing public debt. In some countries these mechanisms brought good results in others have proven to be a waste of public money.

This route of procurement, if correctly used, can bring great value for money for all parts because they all share the risk. The private sector can generate higher profits and governments gain knowledge from the private sector, and access to infrastructures without the capital cost of construction and the population can get access to infrastructure that are going to be used from different generations that will share payments of the investments (OECD, 2011) (OYEGOKE, 2015).

2.1 – Merits of Public Private Partnership

Governments worldwide understand that involving the private sector to bring capital to invest in public infrastructures could increase economic growth making use of the private funds to replace the gap left by the financial constraints (QUIUM, 2011). Other benefits include the introduction of new technology and innovation to delivery better services, certainty in the delivery time and budget, development of local business providing opportunities to collaborate with large international companies and improve the capacity of the public sector to deliver the growing demand for infrastructures by sharing the risk with the private sector and extract value for money during whole life-cycle of the project (WORLD BANK³, 2015).

2.2 – Demerits of Public Private Partnerships

The use of PPPs schemes also showed that there are risks that must be taken into consideration. The overall cost of PPPs are greater than in traditional procurement and the tender process is more complex and the public sector needs expertise to manage that process. The allocation of the risk is also important and the greater the risk is for the private sector the higher the cost for the public. The exchange of capital cost for revenue expenditure has a cost attached to the debt. The public sector is still accountable for the quality of the service provided from the private sector and needs to retain the skilled staff to deal with all situations during the arrangement, performance bound is needed to ensure “fitness for purpose” (WORLDBANK³, 2015).

Another important aspect in PPPs formats is that it needs to take into consideration that changes in the design need to be negotiated and can carry high costs to the arrangement (OYEGOKE, 2015).

3 – PPP Formats

There are a wide range of PPPs formats, typically these models vary in extend of risk taken by the private sector. PPPs are classified into five broad categories and are organised by the sequence of events occurring during the long term relationship between private and public sector (WORLD BANK⁴, 2015).

The basic features of PPPs models can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Categories of PPPs and the allocation of the risk (adapted from QUIUM, 2011).

These five categories can have many variations and combinations between them. A categorization of the PPP models and their characteristics can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2 - Categories of PPP adapted from (QUIUM, 2011)

Broad category	Main variants	Ownership of capital assets	Responsibility of investment	Assumption of risk	Duration of contract (years)
Supply and management contract	Outsourcing	Public	Public	Public	1-3
	Maintenance management	Public	Public/Private	Public/Private	3-5
	Operational management	Public	Public	Public	3-5
Turnkey		Public	Public	Private/Public	1-3
Affermage/Lease	Affermage	Public	Public	Private/Public	5-20
	Lease*	Public	Public	Private/Public	5-20
Concessions	Franchise	Public/Private	Private/Public	Private/Public	3-10
	BOT**	Public/Private	Private/Public	Private/Public	15-30
Private ownership of assets and PFI type	BOO/DBFO	Private	Private	Private	Indefinite
	PFI***	Private/Public	Private	Private/Public	10-20
	Divestiture	Private	Private	Private	Indefinite

** Build-Operate-Transfer (BOT) has many other variants such as Build-Transfer-Operate (BTO), Build-Own-Operate-Transfer (BOOT) and Build-Rehabilitate-Operate-Transfer (BROT).

*** The Private Finance Initiative (PFI) model has many other names. In some cases, asset ownership may be transferred to, or retained by the public sector.

The categories of PPPs most used in the context of road infrastructure are Concession and Private Ownership and they can have many variants namely, Build-Transfer-Operate (BTO), Build-Operate-Transfer (BOT) or Build-Rehabilitate-Operate-Transfer (BROT). In these cases the private sector designs, builds and operate the asset during the PPP agreement. The difference between them is that ownership of the asset in BTO passes to the public sector after completion while in BOT ownership passes in the end of the agreement, in both the public sector funds the project. Build-Own-Operate-Transfer (BOOT), and Build-Own-Operate (BOO) in these cases the private finance, builds, owns and operate the asset for a specified period of time. They differ in the ownership in BOO the private sector owns the facility perpetuity while BOOT transfers it in the end of the agreement. Design Build-Finance-Operate (DBFO) is roughly the same as BOOT but DBFO focuses more in the delivery of a service and not in the asset (QUIUM, 2011; OYEGOKE, 2015).

4 – PPP Approach for a New Project

With regards to the implementation of a PPP format for the development of new roads infrastructures in Portugal, a concession would be an appropriate format as the country already has a mature market in the use of PPPs so the government can manage the complexity of the implementation. This experience can facilitate the hard negotiations between the two parties and the management of future contingent liabilities.

The type of format indicated for this concession is BOT (Build-Operate-Transfer), in this case the private will design, build and operate the infrastructures being the risk of the all operation allocated to the private sector. The private parties can bring investment although the public sector should finance the project. Technology and innovation are brought from the private sector to the project and to the public sector. The public sector owns the asset in the end of the agreement and sustains control on the policy. During the long term relation the concessionaire will provide training to government staff and generate conditions for the operations take over after the end of the agreement.

The concession can generate income by collecting tolls and renting advertisement space to pay for the operations maintenance and construction.

Example: Concession BRISA Portugal of the motorway A1 Lisbon-Porto 346 km in 1972 (FERREIRA, 2013).

5 – PPP Approach for Existing Roads

For existing roads it is possible to implement a Concession PPP format. A suitable type to use should be Rehabilitate, Upgrade, Maintain, Operate and Transfer (RUMOT). Rehabilitate and upgrade obligates the concessionaire to renovate and improve the existing road; project and construction methods are the concessionaire responsibility. The concessionary must maintain the road quality by implementing proper and periodic monitoring programmes and promote good maintenance practices. Day-to-day operations are concessionaire responsibilities during the period of the PPP scheme this involve the implementation of the road safety protocol involving activities from road patrolling, ambulances, break down tow away to tolls collection. Transfer stipulates that in the end of the PPP scheme the ownership of the asset passes to the public sector (Thillai et al., 2010).

This approach has some similarity with BOT used for the new roads. The private sector brings finance, technology and innovation to the project, share knowledge with the public sector and makes the project easier and faster to implement. The same method for payments can be used as well as the duration of the arrangement.

PPP arrangements for maintenance can be a way of maintaining road conditions, traditional procurement routes just cover the construction aspect and no planning for the whole life cycle is taken in consideration leaving the infrastructures without proper care generating a fast deterioration of the asset transforming small maintenance procedures in deep and expensive interventions.

Example: *Concession ECR in India Chennai-Cuddalore 166 km format used RUMOT (Thillai et al., 2010).*

6 – Analogy between PPP Format for New and Existing Roads

Regarding the two PPP described above there are not many differences in terms of format. Both are concession and share the same pros and cons. The main difference is the risk involved, not in terms of the allocation but in the construction process. Implementation of PPP arrangements for existing roads carries less risk for the private sector. As the road already exists, most of the construction risks such as formation of alignment, land acquisition, or environmental impact are no longer present. The construction process is easier to implement as most of the variables are known, a proper planning can be implemented and delays in the project completion and overruns can be avoided. A minimal management of the stakeholders is needed as the upgrade of the roads must be taken without closing the traffic (Thillai *et al.*, 2010).

7 – PFI Approach for New and Existing Roads

Public Finance Initiative (PFI) is one of the first forms of PPP developed by governments to join with the private sector to design, build, refurbish, finance and operate facilities. This approach focuses on the delivery of services rather than the purchase of assets and is used to provide better services to general population since the focus is on the delivery of a service contract arrangement is needed to ensure that ownership of the asset passes to the public sector in the end of the agreement. PFI are usually long term contracts due to the investment needed and a Special Purpose Vehicle is formed by a consortium of companies to contract with the government the supply of services (OYEGOKE, 2015).

The increase on the demand of infrastructures together with the financial constraints that some governments are facing makes an appropriate climate for PFI approach since they can provide the developing of big infrastructures projects without governments finance high capital costs (ALSHAWI, 2009). This means that the private sector will finance and build (DBFO) the project without costs for governments and in this way do not raise the public debt. When construction is complete the public sector starts to pay for the service delivered converting capital cost into revenue expenditure (ALSHAWI, 2009; OYEGOKE, 2015). In this situation the capital expenditure raised by the private sector is paid by the revenue expenditure guaranteed income provided by the unitary payments that are used to pay the debt and operate the asset (OYEGOKE, 2015). These payments can be raised from tolls collection from the users, unitary fee agreed with public sector or shadow tolls (ALSHAWI, 2009).

The capital raised by the private sector, with higher interest rates, than for the public sector and the costs of consultancy for both parts makes PFI much more expensive than traditional forms of procurement. For this reason analyses to ensure affordability and value for money during the whole life cost of the project is needed (ALSHAWI, 2009).

For the concerned project of new and existing roads this approach is highly recommended since the country needs a fast intervention in the development of the infrastructures. Having the private sector collaborating with the public sector is

always a form of bringing innovation to design and management of the assets improving performance in the delivery of the asset and share the risk of the project (ALSHAWI, 2009). Considering the use of a DBFO format all the risk of the construction is allocated to the private sector that is paid to supply a service with pre-defined standards and in this case has no incentive to reduce the quality of the service to ensure the success of the project and get their investment repaid.

Seeing that this programme is for the development of a whole country road infrastructure in most countries is impossible to delivery such a project without private financing support or incurring in a long period of investment.

Regarding the existing roads this form of procurement can also be applied with some precaution since the PFI focus on delivery a service with a required performance and considering that roads already exist some time makes it difficult to achieve the desired performance.

Example: *Concession Lusoponte of the Bridge Vasco da Gama Tagus River 17 km in 1994 Portugal (FERREIRA, 2013). Concession SCUT Beira Interior 177.5 km in 1999 Portugal (FERREIRA, 2013).*

8 – Alternative Routes of Procurement

There are many methodologies for the delivery of government's assets such as infrastructures. All of them have their own characteristics, advantages and disadvantages that might suit different conditions. The right choice for the model can, in some cases, determine the success of a project. A complex analysis should be carried out and the model that brings more value for money appointed. For the development of road infrastructure in Portugal three delivery models were considered; Construct Only (CO), Design and Build (DB) and Design Build and Maintain (DBM) were selected and analysed (CEIID, 2010).

The first Construction only with a Lump Sum or Fixed Price contract is the traditional form of procurement where the client is responsible for the design and documentation. In this model, the process is linear and this means slower because each stage of the process needs to be completed in order to move to the next level. Sufficient time is needed for the delivery of the infrastructure. Since the design is complete before the tendering, it is easier to quantify all the costs and the final price is known before construction bringing high levels of accountability to the process. Low cost for tendering makes the process very competitive. However, the lack of involvement with the contractor during the design phase can create claims and delays due to errors in the design. The development of the project without this input brings poor build-ability and innovation jeopardising the whole life-cycle costs of the project (CEIID, 2010).

The second and third models are very similar, Design and Build and Design, Build and Maintain both share some characteristics. In these models, the client provides a design brief with the requirements for the infrastructure and prepares a tender process for the completion of the detail design and construction. This process is more efficient than CO because construction can start before completion of the design. The contractor involvement during the design brings build-ability and innovation to the project and better management to whole project. Since the design and construction is delivered to a single contractor in Lump Sum or Fixed Priced single accountability is provided. These procurements methods are more expensive than CO due to the transfer of the risks of the design from the client to the contractor and long tender period is needed for the contractors assess the risks. Regarding the

whole life-cycle cost these two methods, DB and DBM have a different approaches while DB does not have any consideration in the whole life-cycle DBM can bring efficient design and quality to construction to ensure proper maintenance standards agreed with the client at a lower cost possible producing a better finish product. This approach is more costly than DB in a short run but in the long run DBM can bring more value for money. Since in both cases the design is the responsibility of the contractor warranty is needed for “fitness to purpose” of the asset (CEIID, 2010).

Regarding the development of new and existing roads all these methods can be applied. For existing roads the CO method is better suited because there is less need for design since the roads already exist. The roads that need intervention can be separated and managed separately in small projects. For new roads DB and DBM can bring more value for money throughout the whole life-cycle due to better management skills from the private contractors. However, with this method the client loses part of the control in the process since the design is no longer provided by the client. Close surveying is needed in the process to guaranty right design choices (CEIID, 2010).

The three methods mentioned above focus only in the delivery of the asset leaving the responsibility of the operations with the client. The client is responsible for funding all the project and is charged with the payments during all phases of the process and whole life-cycle costs.

Example: *Road IC16 Radial da Pontinha 2.8 km (CO) June 2014 Portugal (BABO, 2014)*

9 – Conclusion

This report shows that there are no perfect routes for procurement and all approaches have advantages and disadvantages. The right choice should be made after a careful analysis of the project conditions and circumstances. The format that brings more value for money should be adopted.

Traditional approaches tend to be more acceptable due to high accountability and less complexity making it easier for the general population to understand it. These approaches make changes and variations in the project easier and give a perspective to the population of control from public authorities. However, the demand for new and competitive infrastructures allied with budget constrains from public authorities make them difficult to adopt.

PPPs have gained popularity among governments around the world due to the possibility of develop expensive infrastructural projects without the need of the capital cost and with the possibility of sharing the risk. This method of procurement have many advantages and if wisely implemented can enable countries with a sustainable development in their infrastructures. However, the massive and pervasive use of this method can result in underlying fiscal costs for the tax payers.

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